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LIC OF INDIA'S INVESTMENT IN INFRASTRUTIRE AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES – A CASE STUDY

Dr. S. Chand Basha

Professor & HOD-MBA, St. Ann's Engineering College,
Chirala, Andhra Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT:

Investment refers to acquisition of assets, conversion of money into claims on money and use of funds for productive and income earning assets. Thus, it means the use of funds for productive purposes for securing some objectives like income, appreciation of capital or capital gains or for further production of goods and services with the objective of securing profits. Further, Investment activity involves the use of funds or savings for further creation of assets or acquisition of existing assets. True to the spirit of nationalization, the Corporation has deployed its funds to the best advantage of LIC policyholders as well as for the community as a whole. National priorities and the obligation of reasonable returns to the policy holders are the main criteria of our investments. A modest attempt is made to analyze and understand LIC of India's investment in infrastructure and social development activities. The secondary data are collected for a period of 8 years from 2005-06 to 2012-2013 for the analysis. Compounded Annual Growth rate is used in order to compare the growth rates of two investments and also percentage calculated wherever necessary to draw appropriate inferences.

Key words: LIC of India, Loans, Advances, Investment, Infrastructure, social development

Introduction

In January 1956, 245 Indian and foreign insurers and provident societies operating in India were taken over by the Central Government by an Act of parliament. The LIC, with a capital of Rs 5 crores was set up in September that year. Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru on the eve of the inauguration of the Life Insurance Corporation of India said that, "Its LIC's objective is to serve the individuals as well as the state. The profit motive goes out of it and the service motive becomes much more dominant". The mission of the Corporation is to cover the poor and needy under social security net and also to mobilize public savings through insurance for nation building activities such as funding Government projects, Infrastructure development, And Housing development etc. LIC is a monolithic organization with its head office located in Mumbai. The Corporation divided into eight zones. The zones are subdivided into 108 divisions, which are further subdivided into 2048 Branches. Further, it has 1004 satellite offices as on 31-3-2010 It is having a huge consumer base and is evolved as one of the most powerful brands of the country. Largest insurance Company in the world in Customer Base (23 crore customers) No.1 insurance company in the world in terms of agency (about 1.1 Million agents) LIC is No.1 insurer in the world in Volume & Sold around 3.75 Cr. Policies in 2009-2010. 2nd Biggest Real Estate Owner next to Indian Railways. LIC is one of the highest income taxes playing Organization. LIC Settles 2.21 claims per second, LIC settled 139 lakhs claims during the year 2009-2010. Prompt settlement of claims (97% maturity claim settled on or before due date)

True to the spirit of nationalization, the Corporation has deployed its funds to the best advantage of LIC policyholders as well as for the community as a whole. National priorities and the obligation of reasonable returns to the policy holders are the main criteria of our investments. The investment of the Corporation's funds is governed by Section 27A of the Insurance Act, 1938, subsequent guidelines / instructions issued there under from time to time by the Government of India, and the IRDA by way of regulations. As per the prescribed investment pattern approved by IRDA, the controlled funds are invested as follows:-

Not less than 50% is invested in Govt. Securities or other approved securities.

Not exceeding 35% in approved investments & others Investments.

Not less than 15% in housing & infrastructure.

Review of Literature:

Phaneesh in his article-"Investment Regulations for Life Insurers" examined the regulations prescribed by IRDA for the investment to be made by insurance companies. He also examined the impact of investment regulations on the profitability of LIC.

Venkateswara Rao, BH and Prakasha Rao BKS in their article "Investment portfolio and performance of LIC of India " stated that the higher the investment income, the better the Corporation due to the fact that in claims settlement, in maintaining solvency margins and also in providing benefits to policyholders, investment income plays an important role.

Dodds and Croom in their book, "The Insurance Behavior of British Life Insurance Companies" critically analyzed the investment behavior of insurance companies with an aim to provide guidelines to set the future investment pattern.

Rajadhyaksha Niranjana in his article- "The Rise of Financial Conglomerates" explained the growth and development of HDFC, ICICI, SBI life and KOTAK MAHINDRA Insurance companies. He also dealt with the various activities of these insurance companies and also the key success factors for their growth and development.

Subedhar in his article – "Legal Framework for Insurance" examined the legal framework in terms of the nature of insurance legislation, components of legislation and supervision, product and premium rates, expenses control, asset liability management, solvency requirements, allocation of surplus, investment parameters etc.

Venkateswara Rao in his article, “ LIC of India -New Business Lacks Vigor” felt that though LIC of India retained its leadership share in the insurance market, its market share in terms of new business premium income declined to a low of 78.07 percent in 2004-05. In view of this, he suggested to LIC to focus on key result areas such as improving the productivity of agents, marketing of high sum assured policies and also the introduction of customer friendly plans or products.

Rama Murthy in his article-“Life Insurance Corporation: Advantage of strong Base” discussed the organizational structure and performance of LIC of India. He also examined the various customer orientation programs undertaken by the Corporation. He felt that LIC of India is invincible due to its strong presence in the market as well as its corporate image.

Ram Pratap Sinha (compared the operating efficiency of 13 life insurance companies using the Data Envelopment Analysis. The comparison of efficiency scores of the life insurance companies with the same of LIC show that the private insurance companies are still lagging behind LIC of India.

Objectives of Study

To study the pattern of loans advanced by LIC of India to various development and social activities

Period of the Study

The secondary data are collected for a period of 8 years from 2005-2006 to 2012-2013 for the analysis of loans advanced by LIC of India to various development and social activities.

Statistical Tools

The percentages are calculated wherever necessary for appropriated inferences. Apart from these percentages Compounded Annual Growth rate (CAGR) calculated in order to compare the growth rates of two investments.

Loans advanced for various development activities:

Loans continued to constitute one of the major avenues of investment for the corporation’s funds. In granting these loans, LIC has been emphasizing on financing:

- a) Project/schemes for generation and transmission of electricity for agricultural and industrial use.
- b) Housing schemes.
- c) Piped water supply and sewerage projects/schemes in rural and urban areas and townships.
- d) Development of road transport and.
- e) Industrial development.

The details of the developmental activities for which loans are advanced by LIC have been presented in table 1

Table 1 Detail of Development Activities

Development activities	Details
Electricity	State Electricity Boards/Electric Power Corporations, i.e. SEBs/EPC:
Housing	a) State Government for Housing Schemes
	b) Apex Co-Operative Housing Finance Societies
	c) LIC Housing Finance Ltd.
	d) Housing And Urban Development
	e) National Housing Bank
Water Supply And Sewerage	a) Municipal Committees/Water Supply and Sewerage Boards
	b) Zilla Parishads for Rural Piped Water Supply Schemes
	c) Irrigation
Transport	State Road Transport Corporation
Industrial development	Joint Stock Companies

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Investment in Infrastructure and Social Development Activities:

The loans are advanced for the various development activities every year. It has been the constant endeavor of the corporation to provide security to as many people as possible and to channelize the savings mobilized for the welfare of the people at large. Thus, the data related to the loans advanced for the different years has been gathered and shown in the form of a table in order to make proper analysis as well as comparison of various years regarding the amount of loans advanced to various developmental activities like Electricity, Housing, Water Supply and Sewerage, Transport, Industrial Development.

Table. 2 Investment In Infrastructure & Social Sectors (Rs. In Crores)

Year	Power	Housing	Water Supply & Sewerage Schemes	Transport	Other Infrastructure (Industrial development)	Total	Annual Growth Rate
2005-06	8471.90 (61.17)	4463.97 (32.23)	26.16 (0.19)	128.00 (0.92)	760.81 (5.49)	13850.84 (100)	-
2006-07	9615.00 (55.58)	3968.91 (22.95)	65.34 (0.38)	601.82 (3.48)	3045.86 (17.61)	17296.93 (100)	24.88
2007-08	7022.00 (41.88)	3935.00 (23.65)	14.00 (0.084)	45.00 (0.27)	5749 (34.29)	16765.00 (100)	-3.1
2008-09	6689.11 (30.72)	6734.87 (30.93)	118.31 (0.54)	227.73 (1.05)	8005.55 (36.76)	21775.57 (100)	29.89
2009-10	13044.4 (62.69)	4034.77 (19.39)	47.00 (0.22)	680.87 (3.27)	3001.36 (14.42)	20808.74 (100)	-4.44
2010-11	7616.61 (49.99)	4481.75 (29.42)	24.78 (0.16)	685.58 (4.50)	2427.22 (15.93)	15235.94(100)	-26.78
2011-12	15707.7 (57.33)	7476.81 (27.29)	21.72 (0.079)	1734.71 (6.33)	2457.59 (8.97)	27398.1 (100)	79.82
2012-13	10995.3 (54.33)	4121.74 (20.44)	35.72 (0.18)	0.00 (0.00)	5012.13 (24.86)	20164.92 (100)	-26.40
CAGR*	3.31%	-0.99%	3.97%	45.12	26.57%	4.81%	
Mean	9895.25	4902.23	44.13	512.96	3807.44	19162.05	
SD	3178.96	1389.97	34.098	569.49	2301.67	4329.77	
t Value	8.804	9.97	3.66	2.55	4.68	12.523	

Source: Compiled from the annual reports of LIC of India from 2005-2006 to 2012-2013

Note: Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage to the total

Table .1 and 2 give the detailed information regarding the loans advanced for various development activities.

It can be seen from table that the total amount of loans and advanced for various developmental activities showed fluctuating trend from 2005-2006 to 2012-13. The amount of loans and advanced was Rs. 13850.84 crores in 2005-2006 which reached to Rs. 20164.92 crores in 2012-13. In 2002, IRDA issued new regulations for investment which lead to a huge increase in the amount of loans advanced to various authorities. The total amount of investment in 2011-2012 was Rs. 27398.1 it is the highest of amount of investment during period of study. The compound growth rate of the total amount invested in social sector for the entire period is 4.81 percent.

Considering the percentage share of each development activity to the total loan amount, power sector holds the lion share of the loans advanced throughout from 2005-2006 to 2012-13 except in the year 2008-09. The second major share goes to housing, followed by industrial development and transport. Thus the least share is of Water Supply & Sewerage Schemes from 2006 to 2013. In 2005-06, power holds 61.75 percent share then comes housing with 32.23 percent share, after this comes Water Supply & Sewerage Schemes with 18.89 percent share, the Industrial development holds 5.94 percent share and the least share is of transport, i.e. 0.92 percent. But in 2006-07, there is not much difference in the percentage share of total loans between power (55.58 percent) and Housing (22.95). Also there is increase in the share of Industrial development, i.e. 17.61 percent which is ahead of transport i.e. 3.48 percent. There is also marginal increase in the percentage share of Water Supply & Sewerage Schemes to 0.38 percent. In 2007-08, again there is a significant change in the share of each activity. In this year, power sector has 41.88 percent share, Industrial development has 34.29 percent share, housing 23.65 percent share, transport has 0.27 percent and Water Supply and Sewerage has 0.084 percent share. In year 2008-09, huge amount of loan was provided to irrigation, industrial Development as well as for the housing. Investment in Industrial development is 36.76 percent power has 30.72 percent share to total loans and advances, housing has 30.93 percent share, transportation has 1.05 percent share and the least investment made in Water Supply and Sewerage i.e. 0.54 percent share to total loan and advance. The present study reveals that nearly half of the investment made in power sector during 2009-10 to 2012-13. It is also observed that the least amount of loans provided to the Water Supply and Sewerage. The analysis also shows that in the year 2012-13 LIC of India could not provide any loan to transport sector.

The compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of power is 3.31 percent. The CAGR of housing for the entire period of study is -0.99 percent, whereas CAGR of Water Supply and Sewerage is 3.97 percent. The CAGR of both Transport and Industrial development is 45.12 percent and 26.47 percent respectively which is observed to be highest.

The mean share of power sector is 9895.25 crores of the total amount of loan advanced, housing comes second as it holds 4902.23 crores, Industrial development average has 3807.44, then is transport with 512.96 crores average share. Water Supply and Sewerage with a mean investment of 44.13 crore share.

Summary and Conclusion:

Loans continued to constitute one of the major avenues of investment for the corporation's funds. Loans are advanced for various development activities every year. Comparison of various years has been made regarding the amount of loans advanced to various development activities like power, housing, water supply and sewerage, transport and industrial development. Results reveal that the total amount of loan advanced for various activities showed fluctuating trend during 2005-2006 to 2012-2013 after the entry of private players in insurance sector, the loan amount started decreasing. The compound growth rate of the total amount of loan advanced for the entire period was 4.81 percent. Considering the percentage share of each development activity to total loan amount, power held the major share of the loans advanced throughout period of study except in the year 2008-09. The second major share went to housing, followed by industrial development and transport, the least share was that of water supply and sewerage during 2005-13. There has been a drastic change in the percentage share of amount of loan advancement to various activities after IRDA issued new regulations for investment. The compound growth rate for power loans was 3.31 percent. The compound growth rate for housing loans for entire study period was -0.99 percent which was significant whereas the compound growth rate of water supply sewerage loans was 3.97 percent. The compound growth rate of transport and industrial loan was 4.81 percent and 25.57 percent respectively. Thus, after new investment regulation issued by IRDA, the amount of loans to power, housing and industrial development increased significantly whereas the loan amount advanced to water supply and sewerage and transport has increased substantially. Thus there is a need to invest more controlled funds in infrastructure and social sector as it leads to the growth of economy and generation for employment opportunities.

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